

Making Cultural Ecosystem Services Truly Cultural: Mapping Outdoor Experiences in Ukraine with Telegram

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Abstract. Mapping and assessing cultural ecosystem services (CES) poses a great challenge of quantifying intangible benefits and values. This challenge becomes even more pronounced in context of war. This work-in-progress study introduces a novel, spatially explicit methodology that utilises the Telegram messenger, widely used in Ukraine, to democratise participatory mapping. Our approach aims to explore how Ukrainians value their time spent outdoors and how these perceptions have changed since the full-time Russian invasion. By framing CES as a cultural experience without rigid categorisation, this study uses a location-based service to capture the diversity of outdoor experiences.

Keywords. Non-material nature's contributions to people, Russia, Ukraine, PPGIS, relational values

1. Introduction

The concept of CES has evolved significantly. Saint Marc (1971) highlighted non-material values of nature as integral to human well-being, a notion further developed in economic terms by, e.g., Costanza et al. (1997). Later economic frameworks established CES as an important research niche, integrating recreational, aesthetic, and spiritual contributions of nature into many national assessments. However, such frameworks have been criti-

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cised for reducing the plurality of CES to tangible and straightforward benefits, often overlooking less discernible relational values (e.g., identity or social cohesion). In response, the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) has adopted a more holistic approach, emphasising indigenous and local knowledge to better capture the intangible dimensions of people-nature relationships.

Despite theoretical advances, CES assessments still struggle with uncertainties, often limiting their spatially explicit indicators to outdoor visitation (Vallecillo *et al.* 2019). In countries like Ukraine, which lack national ecosystem service assessments, this issue is exacerbated by the environmental impacts of war (Pereira *et al.* 2022). Existing CES studies in Ukraine remain sparse, necessitating urgent action to address the data desert. Social media platforms such as Flickr, Twitter, and Instagram, along with active crowdsourcing techniques (Heikinheimo *et al.* 2020, Depietri *et al.* 2021), offer promising avenues for rapid CES mapping. Among these, Telegram, the most popular messaging app in Ukraine (Internews 2023) stands out for its accessibility and ease of use. Its functionality makes it an ideal tool for real-time field data collection with a low learning curve for participants (Oxoli *et al.* 2022). This work-in-progress study demonstrates the potential of a Telegram bot for spatially explicit CES assessments..

2. Methodology

2.1. Concept: cultural ecosystem services are cultural

Currently, there is no universal indicator for mapping CES with crowdsourced data. Photo-user-days are widely used, followed by content analysis of outdoor social media posts (Karasov *et al.* 2022). While these methods provide valuable spatiotemporal insights, they are limited by difficulties in capturing less discernible aspects of outdoor experiences and quality of outdoor experiences. Participatory mapping addresses some of these limitations by enriching the range of activities captured, but they often require offline engagement, limiting their spatial and temporal coverage, and comparability (Heikinheimo *et al.* 2020, Depietri *et al.* 2021).

To address these issues, this study frames CES as the **quality of personal time spent outdoors**, a concept built upon Alexander Dolgin's (2012) idea of the quality of personal time, which links economic and, overall, quantitative value of cultural experience to the quality of respective time.

2.2. Methodology: Telegram bot solution

To enable pluralistic, democratic, and spatially explicit CES mapping, we developed a Telegram bot with spatial submission functionality. The bot,

created using the pyTelegramBotAPI library, operates in both Ukrainian and English. It complies with GDPR regulations and has been approved by the ethical committee at the Aalto University. Users from occupied territories or those who appear close to the frontline are discouraged from participating. All data are encrypted using Fernet symmetric encryption and securely stored on CSC's cPouta service in Finland.

The full questionnaire cannot be presented in the abstract given the limits, but key question in the bot is whether time spent in the place was enjoyable, followed by list of outdoor activities to choose from (with a free-text input option), regularity and duration of the visit, travelling mode, noticed changes after the invasion, suggestions to improve the place, and optional socioeconomic questions (age, gender, occupation groups). Currently, data collection campaign is ongoing in Kremenchuk city (central Ukraine) within the local urban development project by the Ro3kvit coalition for Ukraine.

3. Results

The Telegram bot guides users through a series of questions with multiple response options and free-text inputs (Figures 1-2). Preliminary data collected by 15.04.2025 include 181 responses submitted by 169 unique users in Kremenchuk city. Working-age users (predominantly females) report mostly enjoyable and very enjoyable personal quality of time (with older users, 41-60 years old, more frequently referring to 'very enjoyable' than younger respondents). Enjoyable locations are clustered around two anchor locations: Prydniprovs'kyi and Studentskiy parks. Participants predominantly engage in relaxation (nature, sunbathing), communication (meetings, holidays), walking, cycling, and bird watching.

Figure 1. Example of the Telegram bot's interface

Figure 2. High-level block-scheme of the Telegram bot workflow

4. Conclusion

We propose a Telegram-based solution as one feasible way for mapping and assessing CES in Ukraine during the Russian invasion by focusing on time quality as a universal metric. Once sufficient data is collected, the findings will inform recommendations for policymakers on urban restoration and protected area management in Kremenchuk. Additionally, insights will be shared with the public, highlighting potential locations of interest for outdoor activities. We foresee developing a ‘family’ of city- or purpose-specific bots to incorporate quality of time into the variety of ongoing local development and restoration projects.

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